

Separation of Polarographic Waves of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in Potassium Chloride by Differential Complexation with Potassium Salicylate and Iminodiacetic Acid

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Polarographic waves of (a) Zn(II)+Ni(II) and (b) Zn(II)+Co(II) in a mixture have been separated with IDA. The waves are $0.3 \pm 0.02V$ apart in the former case and $0.35 \pm 0.02V$ apart in the latter. The separation of Ni(II)+Co(II) in a mixture with IDA is not reproducible. The polarographic waves of (a) Zn(II)+Co(II) and (b) Ni(II)+Co(II) in a mixture have been separated with potassium salicylate. The waves are $0.32 \pm 0.03V$ and $0.3 \pm 0.03V$ apart from each other respectively. The separation of polarographic waves of Zn(II) and Ni(II) with potassium salicylate is poor as the waves are only $0.1 \pm 0.01V$ apart from each other.

The polarographic waves of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in a mixture have been separated by potassium salicylate. The waves of Zn(II) and Co(II) are $0.2 \pm 0.02V$ apart and that of Ni(II) and Co(II) are $0.3 \pm 0.02V$ apart from each other. A poor polarographic separation is observed with IDA.

ZINC(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) in 1.0 M potassium chloride separately give well defined polarographic waves¹. But when present in a mixture of two or three, the waves of these metal ions are so close that they are almost superimposed, and a measurement of individual wave height and half-wave potential becomes impossible. An inorganic analyst can usually deal with the problem of wave separation by differential complexation. Use of a suitable complexing agent may improve the shape of the wave or bring it to a more readily accessible region of applied potential. Keeping this in mind an attempt has been made to separate the polarographic waves of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in 1.0 M KCl using their complexation with potassium salicylate and iminodiacetic acid (Sodium salt).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR/BDH grade. The solutions (0.1 M) of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) were prepared by dissolving calculated quantities of salts of these metals [$ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $NiSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$] in double distilled water. Potassium chloride solution was also prepared in double distilled water.

Test solutions containing varying amounts of single metal ion, a mixture of two metal ions and all the three metal ions in 1.0 M KCl were prepared. All measurements were made at $pH 6.5 \pm 0.2$. For the purpose of wave separation, test solutions with varying concentration of two and three metal ions in 1.0 M KCl plus complexing agents i.e., potassium salicylate and IDA (3 mM) separately were also prepared. The ionic strength (μ) was fixed at 1.0 by adjusting with potassium chloride.

Current voltage curves were obtained on a CIC (Baroda) automatic pen-recording polarograph.

The capillary used had a m value 8.4 mg/second and drop time 3.0 second at 35 cm effective height of mercury ($m^{2/3}/s t^{1/6} = 4.963 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$). The pH of the test solution was measured on an Elico digital pH meter (Model L1-120). Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution before recording the polarograms. All observations were made at room temperature $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Each of the three metal ions i.e., Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) gives a single reduction wave in 1.0 M KCl. The $E_{1/2}$ values for these ions are Zn(II) $-0.995 V$ vs SCE, Ni(II) $-1.10 V$ vs SCE and Co(II) $-1.20 V$ vs SCE respectively.

(i) *Separation of Zn(II) and Ni(II) waves*: The wave of Zn(II) precedes that of Ni(II) on polarographing a sample containing 2.0 mM Zn(II) and 1.0 mM Ni(II) in 1.0M KCl. The plateau of the Zn(II) wave is reasonably long and remarkably parallel to the residual current. The wave height can, therefore, be measured without difficulty. As the concentration of Ni(II) or Zn(II) increases the separation becomes poorer and the waves are almost superimposed. The problem of wave separation has been tackled by utilizing the differential complexation of Zn(II) and Ni(II) with potassium salicylate and IDA respectively.

On adding IDA the waves are very well separated. The waves are $0.3 \pm 0.02 V$ apart from each other. Under the experimental condition the half-wave potential for Zn(II) is $-1.05 \pm 0.02 V$ vs SCE and that for Ni(II) is $-1.37 V$ vs SCE. This separation of waves is possible only when almost equimolar solution of Zn(II) and Ni(II) are polarographed (Fig. A). A poor separation is observed

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF POLAROGRAPHIC WAVES OF Zn(II) AND Ni(II) IN 1.0 M KCl USING COMPLEXONES (i) POTASSIUM SALICYLATE AND (ii) IDA. SENSITIVITY 0.2 μA/mm.

Concentration of Zn(II) and Ni(II) in mM	Complexones used	Polarographic data for Zn(II)					Polarographic data for Ni(II)				
		$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{2/4} - E_{1/4}$ in mv	$E_{1/2} V$ vs SCE	$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{2/4} - E_{1/4}$ in mv	$E_{1/2} V$ vs SCE
1 : 1	Pot. salicylate 30 mM	5.0	5.0	1.00745	65	-0.97v	7.8	7.8	1.5716	69	-1.05v
1.5 : 1	"	7.2	4.8	0.9671	68	-0.95v	7.4	7.4	1.4910	68	-1.05v
1 : 10	"	Poor Separation									
10 : 1	"	Wave are not separated									
1 : 1	Iminodiacetic acid 80 mM	7.0	7.0	1.4104	60	-1.05v	7.6	7.6	1.5313	90mv	-1.37v
1.5 : 1	"	10.2	6.8	1.3701	60	-1.03v	7.8	7.8	1.5716	90mv	-1.37v
1 : 10	"	Separation is not possible									
10 : 1	"	Separation is not possible									

Note : Without complexone the separation is not possible. Both the waves get superimposed on each other.

when potassium salicylate is used as a complexing agent. The separation becomes more prominent if the concentration of Ni(II) is increased 10 to 20 folds to that of Zn(II) concentration. Other polarographic data for Zn(II) and Ni(II) with these complexones have been enlisted in Table 1.

(ii) Separation of Zn(II) and Co(II) waves : The polarographic wave of Zn(II) precedes that of Co(II) when a mixture of 2 mM Zn(II) and 1 mM Co(II) in 1.0 M KCl is polarographed. The waves were separated by 0.2 V ± 0.01 V but on increasing the concentration of either of the two ions the waves are superimposed. On using IDA and potassium salicylate as complexing agents separately the waves get separated. The $E_{1/2}$ values and other polarographic data have been tabulated in Table 2. Both the complexing agents are equally effective in bringing out the separation. The waves are 0.32 ± 0.03 V apart from each other with potassium salicylate as the complexing agent. The half wave potential value for Zn(II) is -0.99 ± 0.01 V vs SCE and that for Co(II) is -1.32 ± 0.03 V vs SCE. With IDA the waves are 0.35 ± 0.03 V apart from each other. The $E_{1/2}$ for Zn(II) is -1.0 V ± 0.04 V vs SCE and that for Co(II) is -1.35 ± 0.03 V vs SCE (Figs. B, C). The separation is possible even if the concentration of Co(II) is ten to twenty folds to that of Zn(II).

(iii) Separation of Ni(II) and Co(II) waves : In this system the polarographic wave of 1 mM Ni(II) precedes that of 1 mM Co(II) in 1.0 M KCl when a mixture of these two ions are polarographed. The waves are 0.25 ± 0.02 V apart from each other. On increasing the concentration of either of the ions the two waves get superimposed. The use of potassium salicylate and IDA as complexing agents facilitates the separation of these two waves. Though the separation with IDA is not perfect, potassium salicylate helped in the separation of Ni(II) and Co(II) even when the concentration of either of the two ions is ten to twenty folds to that of the other. The half wave potential for Ni(II) is -0.92 ± 0.1

Fig. A-E. Polarograms of
 A. 1.5 mM Zn(II) and 1.5 mM Ni(II) in KCl, using IDA.
 B. 2.0 mM Zn(II) and 1.5 mM Co(II) in KCl, using Pot. salicylate.
 C. 4.0 mM Zn(II) and 1.0 mM Co(II) in KCl, using IDA.
 D. 1.0 mM Ni(II) and 1.0 mM Co(II) in KCl, using Pot. salicylate.
 E. 1.0 mM Zn(II), 1.0 mM Ni(II) and 1.0 mM Co(II) in KCl, using Pot. salicylate.

V vs SCE and that for Co(II) is -1.22 ± 0.05 V vs SCE. The waves are 0.3 ± 0.03 V apart from each other (Fig. D). The other polarographic data have been given in Table 3.

(iv) Separation of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) waves : On polarographing a mixture containing 1 mM Zn(II), 1 mM Ni(II) and 1 mM Co(II) in 1.0 M KCl only two waves are observed. It has been already observed that Zn(II) and Ni(II) waves are superimposed on each other and the other wave is that of Co(II). By using potassium salicylate

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF POLAROGRAPHIC WAVES OF Zn(II) AND Co(II) IN 1.0 M KCl: WITHOUT COMPLEXONES AND USING POTASSIUM SALICYLATE AND IMINODIACETIC ACID. SENSITIVITY 0.2 μA/mm.

Concentration of Zn(II) and Co(II) in mM		Complexones	Polarographic data for Zn(II)				Polarographic data for Co(II)					
Zn(II)	Co(II)		$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ in mv	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ in mv	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE
1	1	Without Complexones	4.4	4.4	0.8865	40	-0.99v	5.4	5.4	1.08805	38	-1.15v
1	2	"	5.0	5.0	1.0074	40	-0.99v	9.6	4.8	0.9671	42	-1.15v
1	3	"	4.2	4.2	0.8462	40	-1.0 v	14.5	4.83	0.9732	40	-1.10v
2	1	"	8.4	4.2	0.8462	40	-0.99v	5.4	5.4	1.088	40	-1.18v
0.5	1.0	Pot. Salicylate 30 mM	2.4	4.8	0.9671	50	-0.998v	5.5	5.5	1.1082	50	-1.32v
1.0	1.0	"	4.5	4.5	0.9067	40	-0.99 v	5.1	5.1	1.0276	115	-1.33v
1.5	1.0	"	7.5	5.0	1.007	60	-0.99 v	6.7	6.7	1.3499	140	-1.30v
2.0	1.0	"	10.4	5.2	1.0477	40	-0.98 v	5.8	5.8	1.1686	90	-1.80v
2.0	1.5	"	9.4	4.7	0.9470	40	-0.992v	6.8	4.53	0.9127	40	-1.35v
1.0	10.0	"	Poor separation									
10.0	1.0	"	Separation is not possible									
0.5	1.0	Iminodiacetic acid 30 mM	5.0	10.0	2.0149	40	-0.99v	3.6	3.6	0.7253	60	-1.85v
0.5	1.0	"	6.0	12.0	2.417	40	-1.05v	8.4	4.2	0.8462	60	-1.35v
0.5	2.0	"	6.4	12.8	2.5790	42	-1.0 v	10.0	3.83	0.6709	65	-1.33v
1	2	"	6.8	6.8	1.3701	39	-1.0 v	7.4	3.8	0.7656	62	-1.35v
2	1	"	4.2	2.1	0.4231	40	-1.04v	11.2	11.2	2.2566	90	-1.33v
3	1	"	6.6	2.2	0.4492	40	-0.99v	11.2	11.2	2.2566	90	-1.37v
4	1	"	5.4	1.35	0.2720	45	-1.02v	15.4	15.4	3.1029	90	-1.37v
10	1	"	Separation is not possible									
1	10	"	7.2	7.2	1.4507	45	-0.96v	60	6.0	1.2089	95	-1.23v

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF POLAROGRAPHIC WAVES OF Ni(II) AND Co(II) IN 1.0 M KCl WITHOUT COMPLEXONES AND USING POTASSIUM SALICYLATE. SENSITIVITY 0.2 μA/mm.

Concentration of Ni(II) and Co(II) in mM		Complexones	Polarographic data for Ni(II)				Polarographic data for Co(II)					
Ni(II)	Co(II)		$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ in mv	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ in mv	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE
1	1	Without Complexones	5.2	5.2	1.0477	65	-0.958v	8.0	8.0	1.619	70	-1.19v
2	1	"	10.2	5.1	1.0276	64	-0.998v	10.4	10.4	2.0955	60	-1.21v
3	1	"	12.6	4.2	0.8462	65	-0.96 v	12.2	12.2	2.4581	70	-1.23v
1	1	Potassium Salicylate 30 mM	9.4	9.4	1.8940	68	-0.88 v	8.6	8.6	1.7328	40	-1.20v
2	1	"	12.0	6.0	1.2089	65	-0.90 v	9.4	9.4	1.8940	42	-1.26v
3	1	"	8.6	2.86	0.5762	62	-0.89 v	11.2	11.2	2.2566	42	-1.25v
1	2	"	15.8	15.8	3.1835	62	-0.92 v	15.8	7.9	1.5917	39	-1.26v
1	3	"	8.4	8.4	1.6925	61	-0.912v	23.4	7.8	1.5716	47	-1.27v
1	10	"	Poor separation									
10	1	"	56.4	5.64	1.1364	65	-0.84 v	11.4	11.4	2.2969	42	-1.27v

Note: With Iminodiacetic acid separation is not possible.

TABLE 4—SEPARATION OF POLAROGRAPHIC WAVES OF Zn(II), Ni(II) AND Co(II) IN 1.0 M KCl USING COMPLEXONES POTASSIUM SALICYLATE, IMINODIACETIC ACID AND WITHOUT COMPLEXONES. SENSITIVITY 0.2 μA/mm.

Concentration of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in mM			Complexones	Polarographic data for Zn(II)				Polarographic data for Ni(II)				Polarographic data for Co(II)			
Zn(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)		$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$i_d(\mu A)$	Id/C	$Id/C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}$	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE
1	1	1	Potassium salicylate 30 mM	6.2	6.2	1.2492	-0.86v	9.4	9.4	1.8940	-1.04v	9.8	9.8	1.9746	-1.30v
1.5	1	1	"	5.8	3.866	0.7789	-0.87v	11.6	11.6	2.337	-1.03v	8.8	8.8	1.7731	-1.31v
2.5	1	1	"	6.6	2.64	0.5319	-0.83v	14.6	14.6	2.9417	-1.03v	8.0	8.0	1.6119	-1.33v
1	1	1	Iminodiacetic acid 30 mM	9.0	9.0	1.8134	-1.05v	6.4	6.4	1.2895	-1.30v	7.4	7.4	1.4910	-1.55v
1.5	1	1	"	9.0	6.0	1.2089	-0.96v	5.0	5.0	1.0074	-1.18v	8.0	8.0	1.6119	-1.42v

Note: Without ligand only two waves are observed.

(30 mM) the three waves are well separated from each other. Though the wave of Zn(II) is a bit suppressed [diffusion current constant for Zn(II) is 0.779 ± 0.4], it allows the measurements of half wave potential and wave height. On increasing the concentration of Zn(II) the wave becomes prominent and meaningful (Fig. E). The waves are 0.2 ± 0.02 V apart in case of Zn(II) and Ni(II) and for Ni(II) and Co(II), 0.3 ± 0.02 V apart from each other. The half wave potential values for Zn(II) -0.86 ± 0.02 V vs SCE, Ni(II) -1.03 ± 0.01 V vs SCE and that for Co(II) -1.31 V vs SCE have been observed. With IDA, poor separation is observed. If equimolar solution of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) are polarographed, the separation is effective. The value for half wave potential for Zn(II) is -1.0 ± 0.05 V vs SCE, Ni(II) is -1.28 ± 0.06 V vs SCE and that for Co(II) is 1.32 ± 0.08 V vs SCE. The other polarographic data are given in Table 4.

The separation of polarographic waves in all these cases may be presumed to be due to the

differences in the stability constants of the complexes of the metal ions under study. The more the stability of the complex the more negative is its half wave potential values^{2,3}.

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